

Synergising Teacher Role Transformation and Digital Competence for Enhanced Digital Learning Quality: A Mediation Analysis in Vocational Education

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Abstract

Background: Rapid digitisation has fundamentally revolutionised vocational education, necessitating not only the integration of digital tools but also a profound shift in pedagogical approaches. Despite this, the specific interplay between teacher digital competence and role

transformation in promoting instructional quality remains insufficiently understood. In this study, digital learning quality is operationalised through four dimensions: effectiveness, interactivity, relevance, and meaningfulness.

Objective: This study investigates the impact of teacher digital competence and role transformation on the quality of digital learning in vocational education. Furthermore, it seeks to verify the mediating role of transformative teaching strategies within this process.

Methodology: Adopting a quantitative explanatory research design, the study surveyed 200 vocational teachers using a structured 5-point Likert scale questionnaire. Data were analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with bootstrapped mediation testing to evaluate direct and indirect effects.

Results: The findings reveal that teacher digital competence is a significant predictor of transformative teaching strategies ($\beta = 0.694$, $p < 0.001$), which, in turn, enhances digital learning quality ($\beta = 0.387$, $p = 0.008$). While teacher role transformation exerts a strong direct influence on learning quality ($\beta = 0.420$, $p < 0.001$), its mediated effect through transformative strategies is weak. This suggests that role adaptation influences instructional quality primarily through direct pedagogical engagement rather than indirect strategic mediation.

Conclusion: The study concludes that while digital capability is a transformable environmental factor, the adaptation of the teacher's role is the primary determinant of learning effectiveness. High-quality digital learning is achieved only when technical proficiency is combined with purposeful pedagogical evolution.

Unique Contribution: This research advances an integrated model connecting digital competence, role transformation, and transformative strategies. It provides critical empirical evidence that transformative strategies mediate the impact of digital competence—but not teacher roles—thereby refining existing frameworks in digital pedagogy.

Key Recommendation: Professional development for educators must extend beyond technical software training to encompass strategic digital pedagogy, including instructional design and data-driven assessment. Policymakers should implement institutional frameworks that encourage teachers to transition from traditional instructor roles to mentor roles within professional learning communities.

Keywords: digital competence, teacher role transformation, transformative teaching strategies, digital learning quality, PLS-SEM.

Introduction

The landscape of learning design, delivery, and assessment within education systems has been transformed by digitalisation. The swift transition to technology-enabled learning during and after the COVID-19 era fast-tracked the use of digital platforms, creating opportunities for interactive learning but also exposing gaps in teacher preparedness, instructional quality, and access to

resources. Addressing these challenges is especially relevant in vocational education, as learning must be sensitive to workplace realities and aim to build applied skills that align with industry's digital conditions. (Hazrat et al., 2023)

The quality of digital learning is about more than the availability of AI technology; it's also about how those technologies enable effective instruction, meaningful interaction, and relevant learning. When employed strategically, digital resources can enhance engagement, autonomy, and higher-order skills. Yet, without pedagogical redesign, technology is often equated with surface-level use, minimal engagement, and incongruous results. Therefore, the quality of digital learning would depend on teachers' ability to implement teaching practices that make technology useful for learning. (Runge et al., 2023)

Previous studies have reported factors hindering the integration of educational technology, such as teachers' low digital competence and inadequate institutional support. Numerous investigations have focused on digital tools and student engagement. However, research on how teacher professional change mediates the relationship between teachers' digital competence and instructional quality remains scarce. This gap is significant because, in the digital age, teachers are expected to navigate digital tools, implement data-driven practices and use technology-enhanced assessment while still meeting professional standards and labour-market requirements. (Lawrence & Tar, 2018; Kallas & Pedaste, 2022; Runge et al., 2023)

The transformation of teachers' roles in the digital era involves a shift from being content deliverers to taking on facilitation, learning design, and interaction management in digital environments. In vocational digital learning, role transformation moves teachers from content transmitters to facilitators/learning designers. It involves orchestrating interactive learning, scaffolding task completion, providing timely digital feedback, and using assessment evidence to adjust pacing and support. Models such as TPACK and DigCompEdu underscore that technology integration in education makes sense only when technological knowledge is compatible with pedagogical and content knowledge to influence teaching practices. From a transformative learning viewpoint, professional change requires reflection and strategic action in teaching as well as technical expertise. (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; Caena & Redecker, 2019; Redecker & Punie, 2017; Mezirow, 2018).

Guided by this backdrop, the present study investigates Teacher Roles in the Digital Era and the influence of Teacher Digital Competence on Digital Learning Quality, as well as whether Transformative Strategies mediate these relationships. Through a structural model that captures the relationships among these concepts, this research explains how digital competence leads to instructional value and differentiates direct, role-based effects from transformative ones. The results provide evidence-based guidance on supporting digital pedagogy in VET, which can inform teacher training and institutional-level policies to sustain the momentum of digital transformation. Synergy is defined as complementary pathways: digital competence contributes indirectly via transformative strategies, while role transformation contributes directly via pedagogical engagement. Simultaneous modelling clarifies their joint effects on the quality of vocational digital learning.

Literature Review

The quality of online learning is not determined by the mere presence of platforms, devices, or internet connections, but by the learning experience—its effectiveness, interactivity, cultural relevance, and meaningfulness. According to the e-learning literature, the quality of digital learning is directly related to how learning is designed and how pedagogical interactions occur, and indirectly to the impact these encounters have on competencies, engagement, and learning. Digital education also needs to be integrated with workplace competencies, such as application skills, data-driven practices, and problem-solving skills, in digitalised professional environments (Hazrat et al., 2023).

Changes occurring in the educational ecosystem, driven by digitalisation, have transformed the teacher's role from a knowledge transmitter to a facilitator, learning designer, digital classroom manager, and guide to independent learning. Several studies highlight that the success of digital learning continues to rely on teachers' pedagogical activity in creating meaningful interactions, setting the pace of learning, and managing student motivation and support. Accordingly, the teacher's practice in the digital age directly impacts learning quality, as it functions at the core of students' daily learning processes, particularly in dimensions such as engagement, clear instruction, feedback, and the management of the learning experience (Lao et al., 2018; Lawrence & Tar, 2018).

On the other hand, teachers' digital competence is considered a crucial foundation for implementing digital pedagogical practices. The DigCompEdu model frames digital competence as more than technological skills, focusing on teachers' professional and pedagogical competencies to enable them to select appropriate technologies for learning, design digital instruction, create digital assessments, and empower students (Caena & Redecker, 2019). Beyond demonstrated knowledge and skills, the literature highlights digital competence beliefs—teachers' self-perceived capability and confidence to enact digital pedagogy—anchored in the DigCompEdu domains (e.g., digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment, learner empowerment) and often determining whether competence translates into classroom practice. Recent research has shown that teachers' increased digital competence is likely to improve their capacity for innovation, the optimal use of LMSs and digital tools, and more adaptive pedagogical approaches. However, a number of studies also emphasise that digital competence, in itself, does not lead to better learning without specific pedagogical adaptations. This suggests that digital competence is an ability, and its effect on learning quality depends largely on how that ability is translated into learning strategies (Dang et al., 2024; Pan et al., 2024).

In vocational education, the qualitative learning aspect is inherently dependent on hands-on training conducted in practical execution environments such as labs, workshops or simulated workplaces. In contrast to more theoretical methodologies of instruction, digital competence needs to be put into practice in designs that allow for the authentic development of skill (e.g., video demonstrations and simulations prior to practice of an act or activity; use of digital job-sheets/checklists and e-portfolios as performance evidence rather than simply artefacts). In this zone, technology should help to scaffold and assess practice—not replace it—by shortening

feedback cycles and amending performance specifications. (Hazrat et al., 2023; Al-Fraihat et al., 2020; Palacios-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

At this point, the concept of transforming the teacher's role is essential. Role shift implies not only changes in pedagogical practices but also in how teachers interpret learning, reflect on their experiences, and adapt their teaching practices to meet the demands of digital learning (Mohamed & Nadia, 2024). There is a strong emphasis in transformative learning theory that change happens through reflection and the development of new frameworks for viewing well-established ways of doing and thinking, as well as studies of teacher professional development, which argue that change needs support, ongoing learning, and active agents of change (Mezirow, 2018). Transformation strategies in digital learning involve redesigning instruction, ramping up technologically mediated interactions, creating more formative and adaptive digital assessments, and using data to improve teaching. Transformation strategies, then, may serve as a mediator between digital competence among teachers and the quality of digital learning (Palacios-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

Even though the roles of teachers, digital competence, and pedagogical innovation in digitised learning have been identified in the literature, current research continues to depict these three factors as autonomous or as a single direct relationship. This lack of integration likely drives mixed findings: competence is often reduced to technical skill, role transformation is inconsistently defined, and mediation mechanisms (e.g., pedagogical strategies) are rarely tested, with many studies assuming direct effects on digital learning quality. The combination of teachers' roles in the digital era and digital competence, and how they interact to transform roles through strategies to determine the quality of digital learning, is scarcely explored, let alone within VET, which has been strongly influenced by industry's digitalisation. In addition, previous studies have largely assumed that digital competence directly affects learning quality and have thus neglected the role of pedagogical mediation (Kallas & Pedaste, 2022; Runge et al., 2023). In that, the present study makes a unique contribution by examining an integrative model and a conceptual framework regarding teachers' role changes as mediating mechanisms linking digital competence to digital learning quality and (b) the distinct paths through which teachers' roles directly predict learning quality. This way, a more fine-grained insight into how pedagogical transformation occurs in the digital learning ecosystem of vocational education is possible.

Furthermore, this research advances knowledge by disentangling two channels through which teacher-related factors influence the quality of online learning. The results suggest that digital competence is instrumental when used as a form of change approach. The teacher's role mainly acts through direct teaching. This distinction helps explain why raising the quality of digital learning frequently requires more than simply training people in digital skills. And it also encourages the move toward development programs that blend teaching redesign, interactive learning management, and reflective practice.

Methodology

Research Design

The analytical research method used in this study was quantitative research. The selected method was based on testing causal (mediated) relationships among multiple latent concepts. These four factors were: Teacher Role in the Digital Age, Teacher Digital Competence, Transformative Strategies, and Quality of Digital Learning. It was possible to examine the direct and indirect relationships among the variables using a structural equations model (Structural Equation Modelling - SEM) via Partial Least Squares (PLS). Teacher Digital Competence and Teacher Role in the Digital Era were specified as distinct predictors of Digital Learning Quality, with the Transformative Strategies modelled as a mediator for digital competence and a tested indirect pathway for teacher role strategies. The application of SEM-PLS was consistent with the goals of the research, which involved prediction-oriented modelling of LMS adoption and testing of complex relationships among latent variables. This was appropriate for the sample size.

Population and Sample

The sample consisted of vocational high school teachers in Indonesia. The sampling method used was purposive sampling by using criteria. Subjects were teachers who practised digitalised learning. They also required at least 2 years of teaching experience, and participants were asked to consent by completing a full questionnaire. Two hundred teachers comprised the sample for analysis. This sample exceeded the recommended minimum SEM-PLS criteria proposed by Hair et al. (2019), which call for 5–10 times the number of estimated indicators. Participants were recruited through professional teacher networks and school contacts to ensure that respondents had authentic experience in technology-enhanced vocational teaching. Eligibility criteria (digitalised learning practice and ≥ 2 years of teaching experience) were used to increase the relevance of responses to the study context.

Data Collection Procedure

The data were obtained from respondents who completed an online survey using a 5-point Likert-type scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). The instrument was developed through theoretical articles and modifications of the instruments found in the literature. Adaptations to the questions were intended to make them suitable for local conditions related to Indonesia's digital education transformation. The instrument was pre-tested on a pool of three academics from accounting education and learning technology prior to distribution. In doing so, able to maintain relevant content and context. A pilot study with 30 respondents was conducted to test the reliability and comprehensibility of these items. The questionnaire was expert-reviewed and pilot-tested for clarity and reliability; participation was voluntary, and responses were anonymous.

Measurement of Variables

In the current study, four key constructs were measured: 1) The Role of Teachers in the Digital Age (X1). This concept was developed and modified based on the Teacher Professional Role Adaptation model (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020) which includes facilitator, motivator, innovator and digital learning manager as dimensions; 2) Teacher Digital Competence (X2)—The DigCompEdu framework (Redecker & Punie, 2017): professional engagement, digital resources, teaching and learning process, assessment process and learner empowerment; 3) Transformative

Strategies (X3/M) -A combination of sustainability learning theory pertaining teacher change development, paired with transformative change development (Mezirow, 2018); indicators discussed were adaptability innovation, reform, and sharing; 4) Digital Learning Quality (Y)—

The E-Learning System Success Model, as described by Al-Fraihat et al. (2020) and its extensions, was investigated through four dimensions: effectiveness, interactivity, relevance, and meaningfulness. At the outset, 12-15 indicators were identified for each construct based on existing models and the literature. Indicators with weak outer loadings were excluded after validation and reliability testing in PLS-SEM. The last model (Figure 1) comprised 10 items for Teacher Role Transformation (X1), 10 for Digital Competence (X2), 7 for Transformative Strategies (X3/M), and the response variable, represented by the 12 indicators of Digital Learning Quality (Y). The measurement and structural models were assessed using standard PLS-SEM criteria with bootstrapping, including tests of indirect effects through Transformative Strategies.

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis was performed using SmartPLS 4.0. There were two main steps in model assessment:

1. Measurement Model Checking (Outer Model) involving the estimation of:
 - a. Convergent Validity by factor loadings, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Composite Reliability (CR)
 - b. Discriminant validity through Fornell-Larcker Criterion and Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)
 - c. Cronbach’s Alpha and rho A reliability checks.
2. Testing the Structural Model (Inner Model Evaluation) consisting of:
 - a. R² (R-squared) to test the model's power of explanation
 - b. Predictive Relevance (Q²) Analysis for checking the predictive power of the model
 - c. A bootstrapping procedure was conducted for testing the significance of path coefficients and the mediation relationship with 5,000 samples.
 - d. Effect size (f²) analyses were computed to determine the strength of the relationship among variables.

Analyses were expressed by means of path coefficients, t-values, and p-values at the 5% significance level ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The research model examines the effects of Teacher Role in the Digital Era (X1) and Teacher Digital Competence (X2) on Digital Learning Quality (Y), with Transformative Strategies (X3/M) as a mediator. Figure 1 presents the structural model tested using SEM-PLS.

Figure 1. Research Framework

In the SEM-PLS analysis results, we find that all the indicators of Teacher Role in Digital Era, Teacher Digital Competence, Transformative Strategies, and Digital Learning Quality have outer loadings above 0.70, indicating that convergent validity is acceptable. All items have been included, indicating that the measurement model adequately represents the latent constructs.

Table 1. Outer Loadings (Convergent Validity)

	Cronbach's Alpha	rhoA	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Teacher Digital Competence	0.935	0.937	0.945	0.631
Digital Learning Quality	0.945	0.948	0.952	0.623
Teacher Role in the Digital Era	0.929	0.939	0.939	0.608
Transformative Strategies	0.918	0.922	0.934	0.670

As shown in Table 1, all the scales exhibited satisfactory internal reliability and convergent validity, with their Cronbach's Alpha and rho A values of each construct being over 0.90; CR = 0.934~0.952 is larger than the proposed level by Hair et al. (2019). All constructs demonstrated sufficient convergent validity, with AVEs between 0.608 and 0.670, suggesting that over 60% of each construct's variance was explained by its measured indicators. These results validate the measurement model's good psychometric quality.

Table 2. Fornell–Larcker Criterion

	Teacher Digital Competence	Digital Learning Quality	Teacher Role in the Digital Era	Transformative Strategies
Teacher Digital Competence	0.794			
Digital Learning Quality	0.607	0.789		
Teacher Role in the Digital Era	0.648	0.660	0.780	
Transformative Strategies	0.760	0.650	0.551	0.818

According to Table 2, all met the Fornell–Larcker criterion in that squander roots of AVE (0.780 – 0.818) are larger than the inter-construct correlations and demonstrated adequate discriminant validity. These findings suggest that the four hypothesised constructs (teacher roles, digital competence, transformative strategies, and digital learning quality) measure distinct conceptual domains, thereby providing a strong foundation for testing the structural model.

Table 3. HTMT (Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio of Correlations) test

	Teacher Digital Competence	Digital Learning Quality	Teacher Role in the Digital Era	Transformative Strategies
Teacher Digital Competence				
Digital Learning Quality	0.621			
Teacher Role in the Digital Era	0.667	0.678		
Transformative Strategies	0.812	0.680	0.564	

The results of the HTMT (Table 3) indicate that all values were between 0.564 and 0.812, all below the suggested criterion, thereby validating discriminant validity across all constructs. This means that teacher digital competence, roles and strategies in transformative innovation, and quality of digital learning are separate constructs in conceptual terms, and the measurement model is devoid of construct overlap.

Table 4. R Square (R²) Value

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Digital Learning Quality	0.553	0.544
Transformative Strategies	0.583	0.578

Table 4 shows that Transformative Strategies ($R^2 = 0.583$) and Digital Learning Quality ($R^2 = 0.553$) have moderate explanatory power, indicating that the exogenous constructs explain more than half of the variance in both endogenous variables (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 5. Predictive Relevance Test

	Q ²
Teacher Digital Competence	
Digital Learning Quality	0.325
Teacher Role in the Digital Era	
Transformative Strategies	0.380

Based on Table 5, the Q² values for Transformative Strategies (0.380) and Digital Learning Quality (0.325) indicate moderate to strong predictive relevance, confirming that the model has adequate predictive validity (Hair et al., 2019) and can reliably predict the endogenous constructs.

Table 6. Path Coefficients

Variable	Path Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values	Annotation
Teacher Digital Competence → Digital Learning Quality	0.040	0.282	0.778	Non-Sig
Teacher Digital Competence → Transformative Strategies	0.694	10.958	0.000	Sig
Teacher Role in the Digital Era → Digital Learning Quality	0.420	5.027	0.000	Sig
Teacher Role in the Digital Era → Transformative Strategies	0.102	1.369	0.171	Non-Sig
Transformative Strategies → Digital Learning Quality	0.387	2.665	0.008	Sig

According to Table 6, Teacher Digital Competence has a significant effect on Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.694$, $p < 0.001$) but no direct effect on Digital Learning Quality ($\beta = 0.040$, $p = 0.778$). This pattern suggests that the contribution of digital competence to Digital Learning Quality operates primarily through an indirect (mediated) pathway via Transformative Strategies. In contrast, for Teacher Role in the Digital Era, there is a direct and positive effect on Digital Learning Quality ($\beta = 0.420$, $p < 0.001$), but not on Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.102$, $p = 0.171$), indicating that teacher role transformation contributes to Digital Learning Quality mainly through a direct pathway rather than through Transformative Strategies. Transformative Strategies significantly predict Digital Learning Quality ($\beta = 0.387$, $p = 0.008$), thereby increasing the quality of teaching and learning.

Table 7. Indirect Effect Test

Variable	Path	T	P	Annot
	Coeffici	Statistic	Values	ation
	ent	s		
Teacher Digital Competence→Transformative Strategies→Digital Learning Quality	0.269	2.688	0.007	Sig
Teacher Role in the Digital Era→Transformative Strategies→Digital Learning Quality	0.039	1.147	0.252	Non-Sig

Based on Table 7, Teacher Digital Competence has a significant indirect effect on Digital Learning Quality through Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.269$, $p = 0.007$), while the indirect effect of Teacher Role in the Digital Era through Transformative Strategies is not significant ($\beta = 0.039$, $p = 0.252$).

Discussion and Conclusion

The study thus found that teachers’ functions and digital capabilities are closely related to the transformative approach and quality of digital learning in vocational education. The R^2 values (0.583 for Transformative Strategies and 0.553 for Digital Learning Quality) indicate moderate explanatory power, meaning the proposed model explains a significant amount of variance in the two endogenous constructs (Hair et al., 2019). Moreover, the Q^2 values (0.380 and 0.325) indicate good descriptive relevance, suggesting that the model can effectively predict digital learning success (Ab Jalil et al., 2022).

There is also a strong positive relationship between Teacher Digital Competence and Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.694$, $p < .001$), thus supporting the idea that digital competence shapes teachers’ adoption of new pedagogical strategies and their practice of transformative activities (Ng et al., 2024). However, Digital Competence does not have a direct influence on Digital Learning Quality ($\beta = 0.040$, $p = 0.778$). This profile suggests that technological competence by itself is not going to elevate the quality of learning unless it is converted into pedagogically meaningful practices—corroborating evidence for the idea that digital competence is a multi-faceted capacity whose influence varies in its translation through instructional efforts (Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022).

On the other hand, Teacher Roles in the Digital Era have a direct and strong effect on Digital Learning Quality ($\beta = 0.420$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that digital facilitation, motivation, and classroom management remain highly relevant for ensuring effective learning in technology-enhanced environments (Boeskens & Meyer, 2025). However, Teacher Roles are not a direct predictor of Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.102$, $p = 0.171$), suggesting that role performance in practice may not translate into strategic transformation of classroom activities. One reason may be that role performance is generally instrumental and proximate, whereas transformation strategies are premised on more reflective, planned experimentation and technology-mediated redesign. This is inhibited in most school settings by poor infrastructure, insufficient professional development, and school cultures that do not systematically value experimentation and iterative improvement (Redecker & Punie, 2017).

The mediating analysis provides additional information about the process of change. Teacher Digital Competence has an indirect effect on Digital Learning Quality through Transformative Strategies ($\beta = 0.269$, $p = 0.007$), indicating that transformation strategies are the primary means by which digital competence translates into instructional impact. Meanwhile, the mediating path from Teacher Roles to Digital Learning Quality is not significant, indicating that teacher roles contribute primarily through direct pedagogical involvement rather than strategic mediation. Overall, these findings indicate that effective quality digital learning is realised through two complementary means: digital competence works through transformation strategies and the role of teachers functions through direct instructional and relational practice.

From a theoretical perspective, the results resonate with the Teacher Digital Transformation Framework, in which competence is part of pedagogical innovation (Redecker & Punie, 2017). The results also align with transformative learning views, which suggest that the shift in teaching practice is not about acquiring new tools but rather about reflective adaptation (Mezirow, 2018). The results suggest that teacher learning should extend beyond technical training and focus on more strategic digital pedagogy, such as instructional redesign, interactive learning design, and formative digital assessment. Schools and policymakers should invest in enabling ecosystems—communities of practice, digital mentoring, and institutional support for experimentation—to enable teachers to transform digital competence into scalable and sustainable pedagogical innovation (Trujillo-Juárez et al., 2025).

VET often digitalises more slowly than general education due to the need for labs, workshops, and equipment for training. Digital tools here are chiefly adjuncts to practice (LMS/communication, video/job-sheets, digital resources, and online assessment), with uptake dependent on school/subject—especially in POD modules, which are limited by time for practice, access to equipment, and performance documentation. This context explains why competence needs to be enacted through transformative strategies and why role enactment is paradigm central to perceived quality of learning.

The quality of digital learning also depends on enabling conditions (infrastructure and students' access to devices and connectivity). These have not been modelled here, indicating possible variation across VET settings; future investigations could include them as controls or moderators. Role transformation may also reflect personal innovativeness; although not modelled here, it may explain heterogeneity in strategy use and role enactment and should be tested as a control, moderator, or antecedent in future research.

The findings of this study suggest that enhancing the quality of digital learning in vocational education cannot rely solely on strengthening teachers' technological skills; it requires moving beyond digital capacity building to embrace targeted pedagogical renewal. Digital skills emerge as a driver of transformational strategies, with the effect on learning quality through transformation having been tested, but teachers' roles in the digital age are only partially related to daily practice. In this sense, a professional development ecosystem that extends beyond technical training is necessary: one driven by principles of learning redesign, formative digital assessment, and

institutional actions that support ongoing experimentation and reflection. For administrators, move from one-off training to practice-embedded support: peer mentoring/coaching, PLCs for redesigning blended vocational tasks, and action research/lesson study cycles. Provide protected time, modest resources, shared repositories (job-sheets/rubrics/videos), and feedback based on formative evidence and student work. These findings can further deepen our understanding of how teachers transform in the digital age, while offering tangible evidence to inform schools and policies for more systematic, long-term development in digital pedagogy.

Declarations

AI Use Statement: During the preparation of this manuscript, the authors used Grammarly to assist with language refinement and editing to improve clarity and readability. All content was reviewed and validated by the authors.

Data Availability Statement: The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Heni Mulyani, upon reasonable request.

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Ethical Approval: This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Institutional Review Board of Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia.

Authors' Contributions: H.M. conceived and designed the study; I.P. and F.K. performed the data collection; R.D.H. and I.L. analysed the data; H.M. and C.C.S. wrote the paper. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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